
FIRM ATTRIBUTES AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LISTED CONSUMER GOODS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA: THE MODERATING ROLE OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE

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Abstract

This study examined firm attributes and financial performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The methodology of this study adopted an ex-post facto research design. The study used ten consumer goods companies from a population of twenty. Data were collected from the sampled companies and analysed using panel multiple regression technique. Findings were that, firm size and firm leverage had insignificant negative effect on financial performance of the companies sampled. Contrary, firm age and firm liquidity had significant negative effect on financial performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Financial performance; moderation, stakeholder's theory, firm attributes, firm leverage and firm age.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

The global objective of profit making organisations is to maximize wealth for the owners of the firm. Wealth attribution is the ability of the firm to have optimal financial performance that creates value of the shareholders. The desire to create wealth through financial performance has been a puzzle for many firms but firms must struggle to meet up with the challenge. In a bid to meet up with the challenge of financial performance, firm must possess certain attributes that are peculiar to address the current demands towards maximizing their financial performance. To be able to achieve financial performance, firms employ every facility they have in the pursuit of the objective.

Financial performance is used to measure the strength and survival of firms in an increasingly fragile business environment where many economic factors are not working in favour of existing firms. This is because financial performance is the basis for the ability of firms to pay operating expenses, pay dividends to the owners of capital and be able to survive in a competitive business environment. According to Ugwu and Eze (2018), financial Performance in broad sense refers to the degree to which financial objectives of firms are usually accomplished and it is an important aspect of finance risk management. This means that financial performance is the process of measuring the results of a firm's policies and operations in monetary terms as well as a firm's overall financial health over a given period of time. Firm financial performance can be used to compare similar firms across the same industry or to compare industries or sectors in aggregation.

Financial performance changes consistently even when the same measure is taken over time this according to Zubairu, Adamu and Abdulkadir (2022) is a function of the changes in the attributes of the firm that causes changes in the financial performance of the firm. These attributes includes but are not limited to the age of the firm, the leverage, the size and the liquidity of the firm. The age of the firm may contribute to changes in the financial performance because of the experience acquired by the firm over time. Firms that are relatively old may have historical advantage as to the type of assets to use to achieve some deserved financial performance. In a similar vein, firms with high size may have the quality and quantity of assets to use to achieve the desired financial performance. The liquidity and the leverage of the firm may change the financial performance the later patents how geared the firm is and highly geared firms seek to achieve high financial performance so as to pay back the debt they owe. The liquidity of the firm settles the daily transactions of the firm which are imperative in achieving financial performance. In spite of the various effects firm attributes have on financial performance, it is important to note that the effects are reshaped by the activities of corporate governance. This implies that corporate attributes may not affect financial performance in isolation of the corporate governance. The philosophy of this study is therefore to moderate corporate governance with firm attributes and see the effect both would have on financial performance.

Firm attributes tend to give companies distinctive or comparative advantage over its competitors because it enables an organization to display uniqueness that cannot be easily replicated by competitors (Alao & Sanyaolu, 2020). Firm attributes are those incentives variables that affect the firm's decisions both internally and externally. They refer to ownership structure internally and externally, levels of diversification, financial leverage, profitability and liquidity (Efuntade & Akinola, 2020). A firm is therefore, required to maintain a balance between its attributes and financial performance while carrying out its day

to day operations. According to Dioha, Mohammed and Okpanache (2018) firm attributes are basically categorized into internal and external. The internal attributes are those management controllable factors which account for the inter-firm differences in performance. On the other hand, external attributes are those uncontrollable factors which affect firms' decisions and which management has no control over. Dioha, Mohammed and Okpanache (2018) assert further that the internal characteristics of a firm are grouped into financial and non-financial variables. The financial attributes are variables which can be derived from the financial statement of consumer goods companies. These include firm size, sales growth, liquidity, leverage, and so on.

The relationship between firms attributes such as firm size, age, leverage and liquidity with financial performance according to recent studies Zubairu, Adamu and Abdulkadir (2022), Alao and Sanyaolu (2020); Rahman, Saima and Jahan (2020) and Donna and Johua (2020) revealed that these attributes greatly shapes the performance of companies. Financial performance of any firm not only plays the role to increase the corporate value of that particular firm but also points toward the development of the whole sector and the overall success of the economy. In this regard firms should strive to maintain sound attributes that can boost their financial performance. It is imperative to mention here that the firm attributes considered by this study such as firm size which is mostly measured by total assets value of a firm can have influence on financial performance since assets are the key driver of firm's operational activities. Firm financial leverage which is the amount of debt a company has in its mix of debt and equity (capital structure) can assist a firm to finance capital projects and take advantage of larger markets for increase performance. Firm age which is simply the time period from its establishment to the present time of existence can be of benefit to the firm since goodwill and other transactions reputation can promote financial performance. Firm liquidity which refers to the ability of a firm to fulfill its short-term obligations as they fall due has a strong connection with financial performance of firms since lenders of funds to the firms usually consider this factor as major yardstick to measure financial performance of firms. Despite the role firm attributes play in positioning the financial performance of firms, current challenges in internal and external environment as well as economic conditions prevent most companies to meet their financial performance objective. In other words, financial performance is a function of the ability of an organization to gain and manage its attribute in several different ways so as to gain competitive advantages. It is on this background that this study seeks to examine the effect of firm attributes on financial performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Firm attributes

Firm attributes are conceptualized differently by various studies depending on the criteria used to define it. Firm attributes are those incentives variables that affect the firm's decisions both internally and externally (Efuntade & Akinola, 2020). According to Efuntade and Akinola (2020) firm attributes refer to ownership structure internally and externally, levels of diversification, financial leverage, profitability and liquidity. This means that firm attributes are factors (both internal and external) that have influence on the general day-to-day activities of the firm. The internal factors are under the control of the firm while the external factors are not under the control of the firm.

Dioha, Mohammed and Okpanachi (2018) identified firm attributes to include; firm size, liquidity, leverage, sales growth, and firm age which are viewed to be microeconomic indicators. On the other hand, the macroeconomic indicators are those factors that are beyond

the control of management. These factors include; interest rate, GDP, and industry size. Dioha, Mohammed and Okpanachi (2018) further posit that firm's attributes are grouped into financial and non-financial variables. The financial characteristics are variables which can be derived from the financial statement of companies. These include firm size, sales growth, liquidity, leverage, and so on. On the other hand, non-financial attributes are those variables which cannot be obtained from the financial statement of consumer goods companies. They comprise of age of the firm, management competencies, and scope of operation.

Firm attributes according to Tresphory and Parameswar (2016) are classified into three basic types namely: structural, market and capital related firm attributes. Structural firm characteristics includes, firm size, ownership and age. Market attributes include industry type, environmental uncertainty and market environment, while capital-related firm attributes consist of liquidity and capital intensity. Umar and Sylvanus (2015) described firm attributes as a firm's demographic and managerial variables which in turn, comprise part of the firm's internal environment.

Other studies on the subject matter maintained that firm attributes include ownership structure, sales growth, board characteristics, age of the firm, dividend pay-out, profitability, access to capital markets and growth opportunities (Abubakar, Isah & Usman, 2018 and John, Willy, Walter & Tobias, 2018). According to Umar and Sylvanus (2015), firms' attributes comprising heterogeneous resources and capabilities create differentials of strategy, strategic choices and profitability levels.

2.2 Financial performance

Performance is the result of the fulfillment of the tasks assigned. Company performance describes how individuals in the company try to achieve a goal. Company performance illustrates the magnitude of the results in a process that has been achieved compared with the company's goal. Financial performance is a determinant of an organization's income, profits, increase in value as evidenced by the appreciation in the entity's worthiness (Abubakar, Isah & Usman, 2018). Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. The term is also used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period.

According to Alao and Sanyaolu (2020), financial Performance in broader sense refers to the degree to which financial objectives of firms are usually accomplished and it is an important aspect of finance risk management. Rodah and Jushua (2020) posit that financial performance is the process of measuring the results of a firm's policies and operations in monetary terms as well as firm's overall financial health over a given period of time. Financial performance is the process of measuring the results of a company's policies and operations in monetary terms (John, Willy Walter, Tobias, 2018). It identifies the financial strengths and weaknesses of a firm by establishing relationships between the items of the balance sheet and income statement.

2.3 Stakeholder theory

The idea of stakeholder theory was originally developed by Edward Freeman through his publication in 1984. It is the extension of the responsibility of top corporate players from the shareholder focus to other stakeholders. Stakeholder theory challenges agency assumptions about the primacy of shareholder interest. Instead, it argues that a company should be managed in the best interests of all its stakeholders. These interests include not only those of the shareholder but also a wide range of other direct and indirect interests. Stakeholder theory holds that maximizing the value of one's stakeholders will also maximize the value of the whole company. This was the original thought of Freeman (1984), but there are still some

doubts whether this is in fact, true. So far, the evidence linking stakeholder theory with improved financial performance is limited, and only few have attempted a thorough analysis of the relationship.

Donaldson and Davis (1991) argued that stakeholder theory is based on the assumption that the interest of shareholders and the interest of management are aligned; therefore, management is motivated to take decisions that would maximize performance and the total value of the organization. The theory believes that there is greater utility in cooperative than individualistic behaviour and hence whilst the actions of management would be maximizing shareholders wealth, it would at the same time be meeting their personal needs.

The managers protect and maximize shareholders wealth through organization performance, because by so doing, their utility functions are maximized (Davis, 1997). To achieve this goal congruence, the shareholders must put in place appropriate empowering governance structures and mechanisms, information and authority to facilitate the autonomy of management to take decisions that would maximize their utility as they achieve organizational rather than self-serving objectives. For Chief Executive Officers (CEOs) who are stewards, their pro-organizational actions are best facilitated when the corporate governance structures give them high authority and discretion (Donaldson & Davis, 1991). This theory relate to this study in as much as firm attributes cut across diverse stakeholders such as financial institutions that lend fund to firm, prospective investors, customers' and the society amongst other who have different interest in the firm base of the firm's attributes.

2.4 Review of Empirical Studies

Zubairu, Adamu and Abdulkadir (2022) examined the effect of firm characteristic on financial performance of consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria: Moderating effect of some key monetary variables using an annual panel dataset from 2004 to 2020. The dependent variable (financial performance) was measured using return on assets while the independent variables were firm size, capital structure, dividend policy and managerial efficiency. Fifteen (15) listed consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria were used as sample for the study. The study used fixed and random effects regressions as techniques of data analysis. The results from the model without moderators showed that there is a significant positive relationship between capital structure, managerial efficiency and firm size and financial performance while dividend policy has no significant effect on financial performance. However, the results moderated with both the inflation and exchange rate indicate that capital structure and firm size have a significant negative effect on financial performance while dividend policy and managerial efficiency have a significant positive effect on financial performance. The study used only one independent variable firm size which is the same with this study however; this study intends to consider other three firms attributes (firm age, firm liquidity and firm leverage) as well as board size and independence as control variables to examine on return on assets.

Shubhi and Archana (2021) investigated the effect of firm attributes on performance in India. The study specifically examined the effect of firm size, firm age, firm growth, board size, and independent directors on a board, on corporate performance from 2010 to 2019. A sample of 270 Indian IT companies, all of which are listed on the National Stock Exchange was used by the study and the study used multiple fixed-effect regression for data analysis. The findings of the study result depict positive impact of firm size, firm age, and independent directors on corporate performance. The growth of the firm seems to have an insignificant impact on corporate performance as sales figures have a recessionary impact. The study's use of many firms attributes such as firm size, firm age, firm growth, board size, and independent of directors with ROA as the proxy for financial performance is quite commendable however, this study intends to use two other attributes not captured by the study, firm liquidity and

leverage together with two of the attributes examined by the study and affirm the findings of the study on consumer goods firms in Nigeria since the study was based in India.

Alao and Sanyaolu (2020) studied the effect of leverage on the profitability of Nigerian consumer goods manufacturing firms within the study period of 2012 – 2017. The study adopted the dynamic panel model. The study adopted ex-post facto research design as the data used were readily available and obtained from the annual reports and accounts of the selected seventeen (17) Consumer goods firms out of twenty-eight (28) listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31st December, 2018 via purposive sampling technique. The multiple regression method was adopted which comprises of Ordinary Least Square (OLS), Fixed Effect Least Square and Random Effect Generalised Method). The finding of the study revealed that leverage has a significant positive effect on profitability. The study's use of consumer goods firms was in agreement with this study and is commendable but only one firm attribute was examined firm leverage. This study seeks to add other three firms attribute (firm size, age and liquidity) with board size and independence as control variables.

Rahman, Saima and Jahan (2020) investigated the impact of financial leverage on firm's profitability: Empirical evidence from listed textile firms of Bangladesh within the study period of 2011 – 2015. The study specific objective was to investigate the impact of financial leverage (short term debts and long term debts) on profitability (return on equity). A sample of 22 DSE listed textile firms has been used to conduct the study. The study's firm profitability was measured by Return on Equity (ROE) and both short term debt and long term debt were used as the as proxies of financial leverage. Pooled Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Fixed Effect (FE), and Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) models were used to test the relationship between financial leverage and profitability of firms. This study finding revealed a significant negative relationship between leverage and firm's profitability. The result implies that firm's profitability is negatively affected by the firm's capital structure. The study used only financial leverage as a predictor variable and used return on equity (ROE) as dependent variable and the study was carried out in Bangladesh. The current study seeks to use more predictor variables such as firm age, firm size and firm liquidity and control variables such as board size and board independence to examine on return on assets (ROA) using consumer's goods firms in Nigeria.

Egbuhuzor and Ugo (2021) examined the effect of liquidity level on the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study with a population of thirteen (13) listed deposit money banks in Nigeria as listed in the Nigeria stock exchange in 2020. Data were retrieved from the annual reports of the selected listed deposit money banks from 2009 to 2018. Multiple regression analysis and the Pairwise Granger Causality tests were used to analyse the data gathered. The study revealed a negative and insignificant effect of current ratio on return on assets and net profit margin. It further revealed a positive but insignificant effect of net working capital ratio on return on assets, and a negative and insignificant effect of net working capital ratio on net profit margin. The study concluded that liquidity level of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria has no significant effect on its profitability. The study used only one predictor variable firm liquidity and based the research on deposit money banks that used much of it. This study includes firm age, size and leverage and control variables such as board size and independence and intends to use consumer goods firms which are non-financial firms.

3

METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this study adopted an ex-post facto design. The study used ten consumer goods companies from a population of twenty data were collected from the sampled

companies and analysed using panel multiple regression technique. The variables of the study were measured as indicated in the table below.

Table 1: Measurement of Variables

Variable Name	Variable code	Variable Type	Measurement
Return on Assets	ROA	Dependent	Profit after tax divided by total assets multiply by 100
Firm Size	FS	Independent	Natural logarithm of total assets amount
Financial Leverage	FLV	Independent	Total debts divided by total equity
Firm Age	FAG	Independent	Number of years of a firm from establishment to date.
Firm Liquidity	FLQ	Independent	Total current assets divided by total current liabilities.
Board Size	BS	Control Variables	Total number of board of directors of a company.
Board Independence	BI	Control Variables	Total number of non-executive directors divided by the total number of board members of a company.

Compiled by the author, 2025.

Model Specification

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FS_{it} + \beta_2 FLV_{it} + \beta_3 FAG_{it} + \beta_4 FLQ_{it} + \beta_5 BS_{it} + \beta_6 BI_{it} + e$$

Where:

ROA_{it} = Return on Assets of firm “i” in year “t”; FS_{it} = Firm Size of firm “i” in year “t”; FLV_{it} = Financial Leverage of firm “i” in year “t”; FAG_{it} = Firm Growth of firm “i” in year “t”; FLQ_{it} = Firm Liquidity of firm “i” in year “t”; BS_{it} = Board Size of firm “i” in year “t”; BI_{it} = Board Independence of firm “i” in year “t”; B_{0it} = Regression Constant β₁ – β₆; Regression coefficients

e = Error term used in the regression model; t = Type of company; i = In a year

4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics describe, show, and summarize the basic features of a dataset found in a given study, presented in a summary that describes the data sample in terms of the mean, minimum, maximum and standard deviation.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Var.	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
ROA	70	3.964	5.298	-10.000	19.000
FS	70	10.864	0.599	8.292	11.684
FLV	70	134.514	91.123	24.000	527.000
FAG	70	48.900	25.960	8.000	99.000
FLQ	70	1.159	0.523	0.100	2.450

Source: STATA Version 17

From table 2, of the descriptive statistics presented above, Obs is 70 which represent the total number of observations for all variables studied for 7 years i.e. from 2015 to 2021 for each company sampled. From the table, ROA is the dependent variable of the study with a mean of 3.96% approx. which represents the average ROA recorded from the sample companies within the period of this study. The average ROA is relatively very low which signifies that all the samples companies ROA were not high indicating low performance in terms of ROA. The maximum and minimum ROA is 19% and -10% respectively representing the highest and the lowest ROA recorded from the firms sampled. The standard deviation of ROA is 5.30% approx. indicating the spread of the ROA recorded from all the companies sampled from the mean ROA within the period of this study.

The table also indicates that the mean firm size FS measured in terms of the natural logarithm of the total assets value of the firm is 10.8545. The figure represents the average size of the entire firm sampled within the period of this study. The logarithm figure is quite high indicating that the size of the firms was reasonable in value. The maximum and minimum figure for firm size is 11.6835 and 8.2924 respectively representing the highest and the lowest FS recorded from the firms sampled. The standard deviation of firm size is 0.5988 indicating the variation in all the other firm size figures from the mean figure. The table equally indicates that the mean firm leverage (FLV) measured in terms of total debts divide by total equity expressed in percentage is 134.51%. This is the average FLV recorded from the sampled firms and the average percentage is quite high which signifies that most of the companies have high level of debts in their financial position. The maximum and minimum FLV are 527% and 24% representing the highest and the lowest FLV recorded from the firms sampled. The standard deviation of FLV is 91.12% indicating the spread in all the other FLV from the mean percentage.

From the table, the mean firm age FAG is 48.9 years approx. 49 years. This refers to the average age of all the sampled firms within the period of this study. The maximum number of

years for the oldest firm is 99 years while the minimum number of years for newest listed firms sampled is 8 years. The standard deviation which is the variation from the mean age of all the sampled firms is 25.9 years approx. 26 years. Finally, the descriptive statistics table indicates that the mean firm liquidity FLQ which is the ratio of current assets to current liability is 1.16. The maximum and the minimum FLQ which represent the highest and the lowest ratio of FLQ recorded from the sampled firms is 2.45 and 0.1 respectively. The standard deviation of FLQ is 0.522 which signifies the variation of FLQ of all the firms from the mean FLQ.

4.2 Multiple Regression

Multiple regression is a statistical technique that is used for analyzing the relationship between a single dependent variable and several independent variables to determine the strength in the cause and effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. However, in carry out the regression analysis, certain diagnostics tests are performed on the data such as normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test among others.

Table 3 Test for Normality

Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data

Variables	Obs	W	V	Z	Prob.
ROA	70	0.953	2.886	2.305	0.010
FS	70	0.897	6.319	4.009	0.000
FLV	70	0.776	13.775	5.704	0.000
FAG	70	0.934	4.082	3.059	0.001
FLQ	70	0.961	2.431	1.931	0.027

A normality test is used to determine whether sample data has been drawn from a normally distributed population (within some tolerance). If probability values are less than 0.05 or equal to 0.05 the sample data has not been drawn from a normally distributed population but if it is greater than 0.05 the sample data has been drawn from a normally distributed population. Going by the probability values of the variables, it is clear that the sample data was not from a normally distributed population.

Table 4: Multicollinearity test

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
FS	1.56	0.641
FLV	1.47	0.680
FAG	1.64	0.609
FLQ	1.65	0.605

Multicollinearity is the occurrence of high inter-correlations among two or more independent variables in a multi-regression model. Generally, a VIF above 4 or tolerance below 0.25 indicates that multicollinearity might exist, and further investigation is required. When VIF is higher than 10 or tolerance is lower than 0.1, there is significant multicollinearity that needs to be corrected. Going by the condition stated, it is therefore, clear that the values of tolerance and VIF in the table are within the acceptable range of values; therefore, there is absence of multicollinearity in the data.

Table 5: Random Effect Model Result

Var.	Coeff.	Z	p.>/t/
FS	-0.601	-0.46	0.647
FLV	0.005	0.62	0.617
FAG	-0.089	-2.00	0.046
FLQ	3.873	2.29	0.022
BS	0.209	0.73	0.463
BI	6.025	0.96	0.335
Prob.			0.045
R ²			0.218

Source: STATA Version 17

4.3 Discussion of Findings

Firm size was found to have insignificant negative effect with financial performance. This implies that firm size cannot significantly influence financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The size of the firm was measured using total assets of the firms, this is to say the volume and value of firms' assets does not really matter when it comes to financial performance except when the assets are adequately and efficiently managed by making appropriate investments and sound financial management that can guarantee returns to the firm. This equally justifies one of the reasons for losses that are sometimes recorded by bigger firms in their reports with many assets. The finding of this study goes contrary with

that of Zubairu, Adamu and Abdulkadir (2022), Shubhi and Archana (2021) and Donna and Wiwiek (2020) who also found a significant positive effect of firm size on performance though using different measures of performance and firm sector.

Firm financial leverage is found by this study to have an insignificant positive effect on financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. This is to say that the proportion of debt to equity of the firms does not significantly affect financial performance of firms. The finding of this study agrees with capital structure irrelevant theory which stressed that the nature of debts and equity in a firm capital structure does not really matter when it comes to performance of the firm. This means that the debt or equity position of a firm have little influence on the financial performance of the firm although, it depends on the appropriate application of the debts or equity that can enhance significant performance. The finding of this study is in agreement with that of Rodah and Joshua (2020) also reported an insignificant effect of firm leverage on performance of firms. Contrary, studies such as Efuntade and Akinola (2020) and Donna and Wiwiek (2020) found a significant positive effect of firm leverage on performance of firms.

The age of the firm is found by this study to have a significant negative effect on financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. This implies that as the firm grows older it does not really mean that its financial performance will increase in the same direction of the age. This is to say that the age of the firm is not a yardstick for improved financial performance except if the firm put in place appropriate financial management strategies alongside with effective and efficient resources management, improved performance might be assured. The finding of this study goes in line with that of Abubakar, Isah and Usman (2018) and Umar and Sylvanus (2015) who found in their separate studies that firm age have significant negative effect on performance of firms. Contrary, the findings of Donna and Wiwiek (2020) and Efuntade and Akinola (2020) reported significant positive effect on performance.

Finally, the study's finding on firm liquidity is revealed to be significantly positive with financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. This signifies that firm liquidity has a strong influence on financial performance of firms. Liquidity management has to do with the appropriate application of current assets and current liabilities for the day-to-day operation of the firm. This is to say that if there is poor or ineffective and inefficient management of firm liquidity it would significantly affect the financial performance of the firm. Most firms usually take advantage of their liquidity position to attract short term investment opportunities that can assist to boost financial performance of the firm most especially in the short-run. Finding of this study agrees with that of Donna and Wiwiek (2020) and Efuntade and Akinola (2020) who equally reported significant positive effect of firm liquidity on performance; although, studies by Egbuhuzor and Ugo (2021) and Dioha, Mohammed and Okpanachi (2018) found an insignificant effect of firm liquidity on performance of firms.

5.2 Conclusion

The study examined the effect of firm attributes on financial performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Based on the study's findings, it is concluded that firm size has insignificant negative effect on financial performance, firm leverage has insignificant positive effect on financial performance, firm age has significant negative effect on financial performance and firm liquidity has significant positive effect on financial performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. It was recommended that consumer goods companies should take advantage of their size to increase their financial performance by utilizing the available assets at their disposal wisely by way of investing into short-

and long-term profitable securities as well as other gainful ventures that can generate additional income to increase their financial performance to mitigate the negative effect of firm size on financial performance. Management of consumer goods companies should consider financial leverage as a tool to stimulate their financial performance. So, they should always take advantage of the available long and short term debts offered to them by financial institutions at low interest rate to assist them increase their financial performance. Consumer goods companies should not consider their age as a factor to increase their financial performance, rather they should continue to research and implement new and better strategies that can boost their financial performance such as internet marketing and other modern marketing methods that can stimulate financial performance. Firm liquidity is a strong factor that usually maintained the day to day effective operations of the companies. Management of consumer goods companies should carefully plan and manage their liquidity especially that of cash to be able to take advantage of current opportunities that can assist to boost the financial performance of the companies.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, A., Isah, S. & Usman, H. (2018). Effect of firms attributes on financial performance of listed insurance companies in Nigeria. *African Journal of History and Archaeology*, 3(1), 1 – 9.
- Akinyomi, O. J., & Olagunju, A. (2013). Effect of firm size on profitability: Evidence from Nigerian manufacturing sector. *Prime Journal of Business Administration and Management*, 3(9), 1171 – 1175.
- Alao, A. A., & Sanyaolu, W. A. (2020). Effect of leverage on the profitability of Nigerian consumer goods manufacturing firms. *Journal of Varna University of Economics*, 64(1), 5 – 25.
- Babalola, Y. A. (2013). The effect of firm size and firms' profitability in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 4(5), 90 – 96.
- Davis, J.H. (1997). Towards a Stewardship Theory of Management. *Academy of Management Review*, 22(1), 20-47. Available on: <http://www.jstor.org>
- Dioha, C., Mohammad, N. A., & Okpanachi, J. (2018). Effect of firm characteristics on profitability of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting Finance and Auditing Studies*, 4(2), 14 – 31.
- Donaldson, T., & Davis, G. A. (1994). The stakeholder theory of the corporation: concepts, Evidence and Implications. *Academy of Management Review*, 20(1), 65- 91.
- Donaldson, L., & Davis, J. H. (1991). Stewardship theory or agency theory: CEO governance and shareholder returns, *Australian Journal of Management*, 16(1), 49- 64.
- Donna, K., & Wiwiek, M. D. (2020). The effect of firm characteristics to profitability of food and beverages companies listed in Indonesia stock exchange. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Law*, 22(1), 69 – 78.
- Efuntade, A. O., & Akinola, A. O. (2020). Firm characteristics and financial performance in quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Finance and Management Research*, 7(1), 25 – 32.

- Egbunike & Okerekeoti, C. U. (2018). Effect of firm attributes on financial performance: A study of selected quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*, 3(2), 42 – 51.
- Egbuhuzor, C. A., & Ugo, C. C. (2021). Effect of firm liquidity level on financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Finance and Investment*, 7(1), 24 – 39.
- Freeman, R.E. (1984). *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*. Boston: Pitman.
- Grant, R. M. (1991). The resource-based theory of competitive advantage: Implications for strategy formulation. *California Management Review*, 33(2), 114 – 135.
- Ibrahim, T. R., & Akinlo, A. E. (2017). Interrelationship between size, growth and profitability of non-financial firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business Management*, 9(7), 76 – 95.
- Jensen, M. & Meckling, W. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of financial Economics*, 3(4), 305 – 360.
- Joan, J., & Joshua, M. W. (2020). Effect of firm attributes on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 11(22), 55 – 69.
- John, K. N., Willy, M., Walter, B. O. & Tobias, O. (2018). Effect of firm attributes on financial performance of listed firms in Nairobi Securities Exchange. *International Journal of Business & Law Research*, 6(4), 22 – 37.
- Kabiru, S., Ibrahim, A., & Amin, I. M. (2019). Company attributes and firm value of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 7(5), 40 – 49.
- Maryam, A. (2016). Financial performance and firm attributes of non-financial quoted companies in Nigeria (Master's Thesis). Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Retrieved from: <http://www.abuzaria/research/publications.com>
- Pearce, J. A. & Robinson, R. B. (2011). *Strategic management: Formulation, implementation and control*. (12th ed.). New York: McGraw Hill/ Irwin.
- Rahman, M., Saima, F. N., & Jahan, K. (2020). The impact of financial leverage on firm's profitability: Evidence from listed textile firms of Bangladesh. *Journal of Business, Economics and Environmental Studies*, 10(2), 23 – 31.
- Rodah, M. N., & Joshua, M. W. (2020). Effect of firm attributes on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. *International Journal of Economics and Financial issues*, 10(3), 255 – 262.
- Shaheen, S., & Malik, O. A. (2012). The impact of capital intensity, size of firm and profitability on debt financing in textile industry in Pakistan. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research In Business*, 3(10), 61 – 66.
- Tresphory, O. M. & Parameswar, N. (2016). Impact of structural firm characteristics on business performance of SMEs: Evidence from agribusiness firms in Dares salaam, Tanzania. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 6(2), 246 – 257.

- Ugwu, R., & Eze, J. C. (2018). Effect of firms' growth indices on profitability of food and beverage firms in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 9(7), 77 – 86.
- Umar, G. & Sylvanus, S. A. (2015). The relationship between firm age and financial performance in Nigeria: A panel analysis. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 17(3), 128 – 141.
- Wernerfelt, B. A. (1984). A resource based view of the firm. *Strategic Management Journal*, 5(2), 171-180.
- Zubairu, A., Adamu, H., & Abdulkadir, A. L. (2022). Firm characteristic and financial performance of consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria: Moderating effect of some key monetary variables. *Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 7(8), 222 – 228.